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THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MONUMENTAL ARCHITECTURE OF URBAN ENSEMBLES IN KAZAKHSTAN

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***Abstract.** Today, digital technologies are becoming more important in the organization of urban space. Monumental objects in the cities of Kazakhstan are important symbols that show history and national identity. From this point of view, digital technologies are useful tools for the design and modernization of architectural ensembles. This article studies the digital development of monumental architecture in Kazakhstan. It looks at how digital tools are used and explains how they help improve urban spaces in both visual and practical ways. Digital technologies help to plan and design buildings more easily and clearly. The study also shows that digital tools can help keep national style while combining it with modern urban design. The results confirm that digital technologies are effective tools for improving and modernizing architectural heritage.*

***Keywords:** artificial intelligence, urbanism, monumental architecture, urban ensemble, digital design, media architecture, cultural heritage.*

Introduction

Architecture is not only about creating useful spaces, but also about forming cultural value and national identity in cities. Modern megacities are complex systems where history, social values, and advanced technologies come together. Because of this, monumental architecture becomes especially important, as it reflects the cultural and historical identity of society.

In my opinion, monuments, memorials, and other monumental objects in the cities of Kazakhstan are an important part of urban ensembles. They fill the space and become its main idea and landmark at the same time. However, due to globalization, cities are changing quickly, which makes it important to preserve these objects and adapt them to modern conditions.

I study the role of digital technologies in architecture. I focus on tools such as BIM, 3D modeling, and artificial intelligence, which help to design, analyze, and protect monumental structures. I believe that these technologies help architects make better decisions, understand space more clearly, and protect cultural and historical value.

The aim of my research is to show the importance of digital solutions in the development of monumental architecture within urban ensembles in Kazakhstan. I think that combining traditional approaches with modern technologies will help create sustainable and meaningful urban environments in the future.

An architectural ensemble can be defined as a spatial system in which artistic elements and buildings are organized harmoniously and united by a common idea [1]. Typically, an architectural ensemble is designed based on a single concept. A clear example of this is Independence Square in Astana, located along Independence Avenue. The avenue includes the Palace of Peace and Reconciliation, Hazret Sultan Mosque, Independence Palace, and the central dominant of the square — the “Kazakh Eli” monument featuring the golden Samruk bird. This monument serves as the main compositional focus, uniting the entire ensemble into a coherent spatial structure [2].

Monumental art is a form of visual art that plays a special role within the structure of an architectural ensemble, as it defines the ideological and compositional core of space. A monument within an ensemble not only complements the space but also becomes its semantic center and artistic

dominant. In this regard, monumental art appears as a synthesis of architecture and visual art, serving as a key artistic tool that ensures the integrity of the ensemble.

Monumental art can be divided into two main types based on execution techniques: sculpture and painting. Monumental sculpture is characterized by its scale, form, and inseparable connection with the architectural environment. It includes monuments, steles, obelisks, bas-reliefs, and other forms. In this study, monuments and obelisks are used as primary examples to determine the role of monumental elements in the formation of architectural ensembles, as they are convenient for analysis and comparison as individual objects. This approach allows for identifying their function as either complementary elements or dominant features within the ensemble. [3]

Every monumental element in an architectural ensemble should have its own meaning and value, no matter how it is made. It is important to protect these objects and keep their original form so they can be passed to future generations. For this reason, modern technologies should be used in design and restoration.

Modern digital technologies include Building Information Modeling (BIM), artificial intelligence (AI), 2D and 3D design software, 3D printing, virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR), and Industry 4.0 solutions. (Figure 1) These technologies allow architects to create accurate digital models, analyze structural and environmental performance, and visualize projects before construction. For example, BIM integrates all project data into a single model, while 3D printing enables the creation of complex architectural elements. VR/AR technologies improve design understanding and allow interactive visualization of future spaces. [4]

Figure 1 – Types of Digital Technologies in Architecture

BIM and 3D modeling significantly contribute to architecture and construction in Kazakhstan. These advancements enhance design accuracy, streamline project management, boost energy performance, and minimize material overuse. Nevertheless, adopting such systems involves high costs and demands skilled professionals.

BIM technology consists of several stages. (Figure 2) It also uses special software such as Revit and Archicad. These programs are used because they allow architects to see the construction plan and the 3D form of the building together in one model.

Autodesk programs are not always suitable for full BIM work, but they can still be useful for visual improvements. For example, 3ds Max can be used to create more detailed and realistic visualizations of the project.

A prominent case is the restoration of Notre-Dame Cathedral in Paris, where BIM, laser scanning, drone surveys, and digital visualization enabled precise rebuilding while safeguarding cultural authenticity. This illustrates how digital solutions enable progress alongside the preservation of historic landmarks. In Kazakhstan, comparable methods could be employed at key heritage locations like Otyrar, Sygnak, and the tombs of Aisha-Bibi and Khoja Ahmed Yasawi. Techniques such as laser scanning and photogrammetry facilitate detailed 3D reconstructions, aiding condition assessments and enabling informed restoration planning. This method has currently been applied to

the Mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi. In neighboring Uzbekistan, BIM technology has been used for several mausoleums and monumental structures to ensure a systematic and well-organized reconstruction process.

Figure 2 – BIM technologies

Today in our country, sculptors use 3D scanning technologies to scan existing sculptures and create accurate copies using 3D printing. This process makes the production of monumental elements faster and more efficient. Many people still have doubts about the quality and strength of monuments made with 3D printing. However, modern technologies and various experiments show that such structures can be quite durable and reliable. It can be said that they are resistant to different environmental conditions, including acid rain, strong wind, hail, and even earthquakes. Therefore, 3D printing can be considered a promising method in the creation of monumental architecture.

(Figure 3)

Figure 3 – 3D-printed sculpture of Abai Kunanbayev

Urban architectural developments in Kazakhstan highlight a deep integration of cultural legacy with cutting-edge digital tools. In the city of Turkestan, monumental structures serve as foundational pillars in defining both the physical layout and symbolic essence of the urban environment. The Mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi stands as the primary focal point and iconic monument, shaping adjacent areas and inspiring newly constructed buildings. Contemporary designs in Turkestan blend

classical features such as domes, arches, and ornamental motifs with modern architectural principles, resulting in a distinctive fusion of historical authenticity and current urban planning.[5]

At the same time, the rapid growth of cities and increasing urban population require the use of digital technologies to manage complex urban systems. The concept of a “smart city” reflects the integration of digital infrastructure, data analysis, and automated systems into urban planning and management. Digital technologies allow for real-time monitoring of urban processes, including transport systems, environmental conditions, and infrastructure performance, which significantly improves the quality of urban environments. [6]

Artificial intelligence is increasingly used in architectural practice, especially at the stage of data analysis and design support. It helps architects work with large amounts of information, compare different design options, and choose more effective solutions. AI tools are used to simplify complex tasks and reduce the time required for project development.

This is particularly important in the design of monumental architecture, where it is necessary to consider not only functional and structural aspects but also symbolic meaning and spatial composition. AI can also assist in analyzing environmental conditions and selecting appropriate materials, which makes architectural solutions more practical and adaptable. Overall, the use of artificial intelligence contributes to improving the quality of design and supports the creation of more thoughtful and context-oriented architectural projects. [7]

These technologies provide new opportunities for analysis, preservation, and visualization of cultural heritage. Digital modeling, data processing, and intelligent systems support the creation of more adaptive and sustainable urban ensembles, where historical monuments are not only preserved but also integrated into modern city life. Thus, the combination of cultural traditions and digital innovation becomes a key factor in the development of contemporary urban architecture in Kazakhstan.

Conclusions

The presented study shows that digital technologies have a significant impact on modern architecture, especially in the design and implementation of large urban projects in Kazakhstan. The use of such tools as BIM, 3D modeling, and artificial intelligence makes it possible to improve the quality of design, simplify development processes, and reduce the number of errors. In addition, these technologies help architects better understand spatial solutions and work more efficiently.

In my opinion, one of the main advantages of digital technologies is their role in preserving cultural and historical heritage. With the help of digital modeling and visualization, it is possible to accurately record the condition of monuments, analyze them, and plan restoration work without disturbing their original appearance. This is especially important for Kazakhstan, where historical objects play a major role in the formation of national identity.

I believe that for the further development of digital technologies, more attention should be paid to education, training of specialists, and their practical application. It is also important to adapt these technologies to local conditions, including climate, materials, and cultural features.

In general, the combination of traditional architectural approaches and modern digital technologies will allow the creation of a sustainable, functional, and meaningful urban environment. This will not only improve the quality of construction but also help preserve cultural values for future generations.

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